

ASSESSING VARIANTS OF LOW-GRADE HEAT VALORIZATION IN THE REFINING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Industrial heat recovery is one of the key features of an economical and efficient production process. Clustering of production units allows for enhanced heat and mass exchange, utilizing heat cascading efficiently, while the options to do so are limited in remote production units. If a stable and sufficiently large waste heat source is available, it can be used either to produce water steam for export (provided a demand for it exists), or to produce power with the help of either a condensing steam turbine or an Organic Rankine Cycle. The presented study investigates waste heat valorization options in a polymer production unit located within a refinery. Key factors impacting the optimal solution are highlighted, including the steam export constraints related both to variable heat demand in the refinery and the operation of marginal steam source. Basic energy and economic indicators are calculated.

Introduction

Industrial production belongs to major primary energy consumers and is, likewise, one of the major sources of atmospheric pollution worldwide¹. Substantial effort is thus directed to reducing the energy intensity by means of both implementing new, more efficient technologies, and improving the energy management of industrial enterprises^{2,3}. One of the factors that, despite numerous actions already undertaken^{4,5}, still offers remarkable potential to contribute to industrial production sustainability is industrial waste heat and its utilization⁶. Solely in Germany, a study by Brueckner et al.⁷ estimated the industrial waste heat availability as 127 PJ/a, or 13 % of total industrial fuel consumption. Likewise, its availability in the UK was 144 PJ/a, according to Jouhara et al.⁸. Industrial waste heat results from heat cascading as well as from exotherm processes. Its internal recovery and recuperation are one of the key pillars of economic feasibility of any industrial production. In case of industrial clusters, recuperation and heat sharing options are widened by the possibilities and synergies resulting from material and energy exchange between production units forming the cluster^{9,10}. Means of waste heat valorization are enriched by the options to convert it either to cold by absorption cooling¹¹, or to electricity¹² by Steam or Organic Rankine Cycle, or to increase its value by utilizing a heat pump¹³. Factors affecting the right waste heat valorization route include but are not limited to: heat source abundance and its mean temperature, heat availability character (continuous/periodic/irregular), annual heat availability, type and character of production process and available infrastructure for heat transport^{14,15}. The hierarchy of priorities starts with local heat recovery and recuperation, being the cheapest and most effective option¹⁶. Rest of available waste heat can be transported to adjacent units to replace heat utilities there, or, alternatively, to the nearby municipality to cover seasonal district heating demand^{17,18}. Usually, option with the lowest priority is transforming the waste heat to electricity^{2,19}. Multiple options have to be considered in parallel, though, as the optimal solution^{20,21}, identified by techno-economic analysis, might be a combination of several options²². This study focuses on waste heat formed in a polymerization process, with the production unit being incorporated in a refining and petrochemical complex. Heat export in form of low-pressure steam, or in form of middle-pressure steam are considered with respect to real plant's production features and the operation regimes of the combined heat and power plant, serving as the steam source for the industrial complex. Alternatives including power production via a steam or Organic Rankine Cycle are evaluated as well.

Methodology

Waste heat from polymerization process is considered, released at a temperature of 180 °C. Annual polymer production rate of 250 thousand tons is supposed. Polymerization reactor is cooled by hot-water loop. This energy in hot-water stream is then available for wide variety of uses. In this work, the production of power by steam is compared to that by Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC).

Figure 1 shows the components of the power production either by steam (a) or by ORC (b). The hot-water stream delivers the thermal energy to water/ORC medium in heat exchanger, where it is evaporated. Saturated steam passes to turbine and performs work. This work is converted to electric energy by a generator. On the turbine

exit, it condenses in condenser and transmits heat to cooling water circuit. Cooling water is cooled in a cooling tower by air with variable temperature, differing according to the season of the year. Water condensate passes to deaerator, where it is deaerated by steam. ORC condensates are pumped directly to the heat exchanger.

Figure 1. Scheme of the power production by steam (a) and by ORC (b), HE – heat exchanger.

Table I
Summary of critical parameters of the chosen working fluids.

Working fluid	IUPAC name	T _c [°C]	P _c [MPa]
R245fa	1,1,1,3,3-pentafluoropropane	154.01	3.651
R123	2,2-dichloro-1,1,1-trifluoroethane	183.68	3.662
R1233zd(E)	trans-1-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoropropene	166.45	3.624
R600	butane	151.98	3.796
R601	pentane	196.55	3.370
R601a	isopentane	187.20	3.378
R365mfc	1,1,1,3,3-pentafluorobutane	186.85	3.266
R245ca	1,1,2,2,3-pentafluoropropane	174.42	3.925
R21	dichlorofluoromethane	178.33	5.181
R141b	1,1-dichloro-1-fluoroethane	204.35	4.212

Preliminary selection of working fluids was done based on the critical parameters of the fluids. Operation parameters were chosen to be lower than the corresponding critical parameters, in order to ensure subcritical operation, see Table I.

The basic mass flows and energy indicators of the power production by either SRC or ORC were calculated by the material and energy balances of the main components, Table II and Table III. Electric energy consumption in compressor, pumps, and ventilators was calculated, as well as the net power produced by steam and by ORC.

Table II
Summary of equations for SRC.

Name of equation	Equation
Heat flow in reactor	$\dot{Q}_D = \dot{m} \cdot \Delta_r h$
EB of reactor	$\dot{m}_1(h_1 - h_2) = \dot{Q}_D$
EB of heat exchanger	$\dot{m}_1 \cdot (h_1 - h_2) = \dot{m}_3 \cdot (h_3 - h_9)$
MB of heat exchanger and pump1	$\dot{m}_3 = \dot{m}_8 = \dot{m}_9$
MB of deaerator	$\dot{m}_5 + \dot{m}_7 = \dot{m}_8$
EB of deaerator	$\dot{m}_5 \cdot h_5 + \dot{m}_7 \cdot h_7 = \dot{m}_8 \cdot h_8$
Mass flow of steam to turbine	$\dot{m}_4 = \dot{m}_3 - \dot{m}_5$
MB of steam turbine and condenser	$\dot{m}_4 = \dot{m}_6 = \dot{m}_7$
MB of condenser	$\dot{m}_{10} = \dot{m}_{11}$
EB of condenser	$\dot{m}_6 \cdot (h_6 - h_7) = \dot{m}_{10} \cdot (h_{11} - h_{10})$
MB of cooling tower	$\dot{m}_G \cdot (\bar{Y}_{17} - \bar{Y}_{16}) = \dot{m}_{12} - \dot{m}_{13}$
EB of cooling tower	$\dot{m}_{12} \cdot h_{12} + \dot{m}_G \cdot h_{\bar{Y}_{16}} = \dot{m}_{13} \cdot h_{13} + \dot{m}_G \cdot h_{\bar{Y}_{17}}$
Relative mass fraction	$\bar{Y} = \frac{M_w \cdot \varphi \cdot p_w^\circ}{M_G \cdot (p - \varphi \cdot p_w^\circ)}$
Mass flow of blowdown from cooling tower pool	$\dot{m}_{15} = 1/3 \cdot \dot{m}_{14}$
MB of cooling tower pool	$\dot{m}_{13} + \dot{m}_{14} = \dot{m}_{10} + \dot{m}_{15}$
Power production	$P_{el} = \eta_{mech} \cdot \dot{m}_4 \cdot (h_4 - h_6)$
Power consumption by pump1	$P_{pump1} = \frac{\dot{V}_8 \cdot (p_9 - p_8)}{\eta_{pump}}$
Power consumption by pump2	$P_{pump2} = \frac{\dot{V}_{11} \cdot \Delta p_{pump2}}{\eta_{pump}}$
Power consumption by ventilator	$P_{vent} = \frac{\dot{V}_{16} \cdot \Delta p_{vent}}{\eta_{vent}}$

Table III
Summary of equations for ORC.

Name of equation	Equation
Heat flow	$\dot{Q}_D = \dot{m} \cdot \Delta_r h$
EB of reactor	$\dot{m}_1(h_1 - h_2) = \dot{Q}_D$
EB of heat exchanger	$\dot{m}_1 \cdot (h_1 - h_2) = \dot{G} \cdot (h_3 - h_6)$
Power production	$P_{el} = \eta_{mech} \cdot \dot{G} \cdot (h_4 - h_6)$
MB of condenser	$\dot{m}_{CW} = \dot{m}_8 = \dot{m}_7$
EB of condenser	$\dot{m}_{CW} \cdot (h_8 - h_7) = \dot{G} \cdot (h_4 - h_5)$
MB of cooling tower	$\dot{m}_G \cdot (\bar{Y}_{14} - \bar{Y}_{13}) = \dot{m}_9 - \dot{m}_{10}$
EB of cooling tower	$\dot{m}_9 \cdot h_9 + \dot{m}_G \cdot h_{\bar{Y}_{13}} = \dot{m}_{10} \cdot h_{10} + \dot{m}_G \cdot h_{\bar{Y}_{14}}$
Mass flow of blowdown from cooling tower pool	$\dot{m}_{12} = 1/3 \cdot \dot{m}_{11}$
MB of cooling tower pool	$\dot{m}_{10} + \dot{m}_{11} = \dot{m}_7 + \dot{m}_{12}$
Power consumption by pump1	$P_{pump1} = \frac{\dot{V}_8 \cdot (p_9 - p_8)}{\eta_{pump}}$
Power consumption by pump2	$P_{pump2} = \frac{\dot{V}_{11} \cdot \Delta p_{pump2}}{\eta_{pump}}$
Power consumption by ventilator	$P_{vent} = \frac{\dot{V}_{13} \cdot \Delta p_{vent}}{\eta_{vent}}$

Table II and Table III: MB – mass balance, EB – energy balance, \dot{Q}_D - heat flow in reactor, \dot{m} - mass flow of polyethylene, $\Delta_r h$ - standard enthalpy of reaction ($\Delta_r h = -3500 \text{ kJ/kg}$)²³, h - specific enthalpy, \dot{m}_G - mass flow of dry air in cooling tower, $h_{\bar{Y}}$ - specific enthalpy of moist air, \bar{Y} - relative mass fraction, M_w and M_G - molar mass of water and dry air, φ - relative humidity (φ on the entry is supposed equal to 0.4 and on the exit it equals to

0.9), p_w° - saturated vapour pressure, p - pressure, P_{el} - power produced by turbine, η_{mech} - mechanical efficiency of turbine ($\eta_{mech}=0.95$), P_i (i = pump1, pump2, ventilator) - power consumption, \dot{V} - volumetric flow, η_i (i = pump1, pump2, ventilator) – total efficiency ($\eta_i = 0.85$), Δp_{pump2} – pressure difference in pump2 ($\Delta p_{pump2} = 200 \text{ kPa}$), Δp_{vent} – pressure difference in ventilator ($\Delta p_{vent} = 0.2 \text{ kPa}$), \dot{G} – mass flow of working fluid, \dot{m}_{CW} – mass flow of cooling water.

Results

The amount of produced electric energy depends on ambient temperature, varying seasonally. Cooling water temperature affects the condensation temperature, as well as the condensation pressure of the working fluid. In winter, it is possible to expand the working fluid to lower pressure, and, therefore, to produce more electricity, as is documented by power production for individual ORC working fluids in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Power production based on the working fluid in winter and summer conditions.

The difference in the working fluids sensitivity to cooling water temperature is caused by their different thermodynamic features (different p-h diagrams), as documented in Figure 3. The power output differences vary significantly and unique features of individual working fluids impact thus the ORC design and its operation as well.

Figure 3. The difference in power production, comparing winter and summer conditions.

According to Table IV, ten ORC media were considered, from which the most perspective was chosen. They were considered according to three main criteria (environmental, safety and technical).

Environmental effect of the working fluid was judged according to two parameters, ODP (Ozone depletion potential) and GWP (Global warming potential). Based on the Regulation (EU) No 517/2014 of the European

Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on fluorinated greenhouse gases and repealing Regulation (EC) No 842/2006²⁴, working fluids with ODP higher than 0 and GWP higher than 2500 were eliminated (R123, R21, R141b).

Considering safety criteria, working fluids were classified into 6 safety groups (A1, A2, A3, B1, B2, B3). Letter A symbolizes low toxic fluids and B are high toxic fluids. Working media with number 1 are non-flammable, 2 are flammable and 3 are explosive. Working fluids belonging to groups A3 and B1 were eliminated from further consideration (R245fa, R123, R600, R601, R601a, R21).

Remaining fluids were considered according to the technical criteria, following produced net power.

Based on the environmental, safety and technical criteria, R1233zd(E) was determined as the medium with the most suitable features for power production from low potential heat from polymer production process.

Table IV

Comparison of the organic working fluids, a²⁵, b²⁶, c²⁷, d²⁸, e²⁹, f³⁰, g³¹, h³², i³³, j³⁴.

Working fluid	ODP	GWP	Safety	P _{el,net} [MW]
R245fa	0 ^a	950 ^a	B1 ^b	3.777
R123	0.022 ^a	76 ^a	B1 ^b	4.366
R1233zd(E)	0 ^c	1 ^c	A1 ^d	4.313
R600	0 ^a	20 ^a	A3 ^b	3.843
R601	0 ^e	11 ^e	A3 ^e	4.124
R601a	0 ^f	5 ^f	A3 ^b	4.039
R365mfc	0 ^g	782 ^g	A2 ^h	3.993
R245ca	0 ⁱ	693 ⁱ	-	4.055
R21	0.01 ^a	210 ^a	B1 ^b	4.388
R141b	0.12 ^a	713 ^a	A2 ^j	4.444

Steam, on the contrary to ORC media, leaves the turbine as wet steam, which requires the turbine to be manufactured from more durable, and, thus, more expensive materials. However, Table V shows that comparing water as a working fluid and R1233zd(E), water has superior features as it is environmentally friendly, non-toxic, non-flammable, cheap and even more technically suitable working medium for power production.

Table V

Results of the system using R1233zd(E) and water steam as the working fluid.

Name	T _c [°C]	P _c [MPa]	\dot{G} [t/h]	P _{el} [MW]	P _{self} [kW]	P _{el,net} [MW]	η_{el} [%]
trans-1-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoropropene	166.45	3.624	455.3	4.8	493.0	4.3	14.1
			479.7	4.3	504.5	3.8	12.5
water	374.15	22.129	48.2	5.5	235.7	5.3	17.1
			48.2	4.9	242.6	4.7	15.2

Conclusions

The aim of this work was to create a model and calculate the main parameters of power production from waste heat in refinery by ORC and SRC, as well as to choose the most perspective working fluid.

To conclude, the most perspective working fluid in this case is water. It is environmentally friendly, safe, accessible, cheap, and even the most technically effective. Efficiency of the electric energy production by steam is more than 17 %. Using water as a working fluid, 5.3 MW of net power can be produced in winter conditions and 4.7 MW in summer conditions. The most feasible ORC working medium, R1233zd(E), delivers net power output lower by around 0.5 MW, compared to net power production by water steam.

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